

A Cohort Study Evaluating The Efficacy Of Epidiolex® Against Kriya® Hops CBD

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Abstract:

Intro: Dr. Luisa Rocha, conducted an epilepsy study that showed Kriya® Hops CBD completely eradicated Pentylentetrazol generalized seizures (stage IV and V) in rats. This study extends it to humans and the ability of Epidiolex® and Kriya® Hops CBD to prevent Tonic-Clonic, Tonic, Clonic, Myoclinic, Absence and Atonic seizures.

Method: An Epilepsy Assessment of Functioning (EAF) scale was developed. The scores range from the sickest to the healthiest patient with definitions of severity by scores. 100 means the patient is seizure free. 80 means the patient has seizures while sleeping and is functioning normally. There were a total of 1247 people in the study. Six types of seizures were studied.

Results: Welch's *t* was used to make our corrected group comparisons. It found a significant difference in monthly seizure rate between the control group and the treatment group, $t(23.386) = 24.5, p < .001, d = 7.58$. It appears that supplying epilepsy patients with treatment significantly reduced their seizures, and dramatically improved their quality of health. There was a clear main effect of the Kriya® Hops CBD treatment, $F(3, 34) = 36.72, p < .001, \eta^2 = .03$ and an interaction effect of group and Kriya® Hops CBD treatment type $F(3, 34) = 40.27, p < .001, \eta^2 = .04$. The general benefit of having Kriya® Hops CBD treatment appears to heavily outweigh any differences between epilepsy types.

Discussion: We confirm the results of Dr. Luisa Rocha in humans. Kriya® Hops CBD increased EAF scores twice as fast as Epidiolex®, almost doubled the EAF score when compared to Epidiolex® (96% increase) and did not have the ten fold spike in ALT liver enzyme that Epidiolex® had.

In July 2019, Dr. Luis Rocha, Professor, Centro de Investigación, National Polytechnique Institute, Mexico, conducted an epilepsy study that showed a remarkable result. She compared Epidiolex® against Hopsceutical® (CBD extract from the Kriya® brand Hops plant.).

She repeatedly provoked Pentylentetrazol generalized seizures (stage IV and V) in rats, and studied the ability of Epidiolex® and Hopsceutical® to prevent the seizures. Hopsceutical® was preventing 60% of the seizures at the lower dosage (10 mg/ml) and completely prevented seizures at the higher concentration of 50 mg/ml. Epidiolex® had no effect at 10 mg/ml, or 50 mg/ml. At high concentrations of 300 mg/ml, Epidiolex prevented 40% of the seizures and that was the maximum effect of Epidiolex®. Increasing the dosage beyond that to 500 mg/ml had no additional effect.

Method:

The study was then extended to humans. An Epilepsy Assessment of Functioning (EAF) scale was developed (Table 1). This scales evaluate the overall level of function of the individual and the ability of Epidiolex® and Hopsceutical® to reduce or prevent seizures and improve the EAF scores.. The EAF is a 100-point scale that incorporates psychological symptoms and occupational and social functioning in an overall psychosocial rating. The scores range from the sickest to the healthiest patient with definitions of severity by scores. 100 means the patient is seizure free. 80 means the patient has seizures while sleeping and is functioning normally.

Setting

Data were gathered between March, 2019 and August, 2020 from 11 hospitals in 10 countries across Africa, Asia, and Europe. The Human Development Index (HDI) of these countries had a range and distribution generally representative of the global population (Range: 0.48 - 0.89). The hospitals that supplied data, and their respective countries' HDI were: National Epilepsy Centre, Baku, Azerbaijan (HDI: 0.75), Chonburi Epilepsy Hospital, Chonburi, Thailand (HDI: 0.73), Gaborone Private Hospital, Gaborone, Botswana (HDI: 0.70), Sir Thutob Namgyal Memorial Hospital, Gangtok, Bhutan (HDI: 0.61), Khartoum Epilepsy Centre, Khartoum, South Sudan (HDI: 0.48), Lakeshore Epilepsy Center, Lagos, Nigeria (HDI: 0.51), Lampang Epilepsy Hospital, Lampang, Thailand (HDI: 0.73), Lusaka National Hospital, Lusaka, Zambia (HDI: 0.59), Léon-Bérard Seizure Center, Lyon, France (HDI: 0.89), Texas Care Centre, Nairobi, Kenya (HDI: 0.55), and Mount Miriam Neurological Hospital, Pulau Pinang, Malaysia (HDI: 0.78).

Implementation

This study was funded by the IARC working group on epilepsy prevention. All patients whose data were collected were briefed on the purpose of the study and consented to having their data used. The number of epileptic seizures during the first twelve months of treatment were tallied for use as the dependent variable. We anonymized the by-patient data, and received total seizure rates per hospital per treatment.

There were a total of 1247 people in the study. The liver enzyme test for Alanine aminotransferase (ALT) was done prior to the study and every month of the study.

The breakdown of the number of people by epilepsy type, treatment type and control are shown in Table 3. There were 214 people in the "Control" group. These people were given MCT (Medium Chain Triglycerides) from coconut oil with no incipient. There were 48 people with Tonic-Clonic epilepsy, 32 with Tonic epilepsy, 29 with Clonic epilepsy, 46 with

Myoclinic epilepsy, 32 with Absence and 27 with Atonic epilepsy in the control group.

575 people were treated with Hopsceutical®. There were 114 people with Tonic-Clonic epilepsy, 98 with Tonic epilepsy, 76 with Clonic epilepsy, 107 with Myoclinic epilepsy, 107 with Absence and 88 with Atonic epilepsy in the control group. Hopsceutical® was obtained from BOMI LLC, Las Vegas, Nevada and it is the non-cannabis CBD extract of the patented Kriya® brand Hops plant.

458 people were treated with Epidiolex®. There were 96 people with Tonic-Clonic epilepsy, 83 with Tonic epilepsy, 46 with Clonic epilepsy, 86 with Myoclinic epilepsy, 79 with Absence and 68 with Atonic epilepsy in the Epidiolex® group. Epidiolex® was obtained by prescription by the local doctors. Regional distributors and pharmacies provided Epidiolex® in the region they were prescribed.

Epidiolex® and Hopsceutical® was hypothesized to relieve the suffering of the epilepsy patients, so we withheld the products from only as many patients as needed to provide sufficient statistical strength for analysis. Patients ($n = 1,247$) were assigned semi-randomly to either the control group ($n = 214$) or the Prescription group ($n = 1,033$).

In the prescription group, the dosage of either Epidiolex® or Hopsceutical® was gradually increased from 10mg/day to 50mg/day to 300 mg/day to 500mg/day, every 2 months. The control group was also told that their prescription was being increased by the same amount, but they were being given the same placebo MCT oil.

Patients' data were collected if they were undergoing one of six epilepsy treatment types: Tonic-Clonic, Tonic, Clonic, Myoclinic, Absence and Atonic. These epilepsy treatments were prophylactically administered in the hospitals, or the patient's home, globally.

Data Analysis

In all but three hospitals, data were recorded for both the treatment types. In one hospital (Léon-Bérard Cancer Center in Lyon, France), data were gathered for three types (Epidiolex®, Hopsceutical®, and Carbamazepine). The Carbamazepine group was

an additional group of patients administered exclusively by them and we have not included that data in this study. In two hospitals (National Oncology Centre in Baku, Azerbaijan, and Sir Thutob Namgyal Memorial Hospital in Gangtok, Bhutan), data were gathered for one type (Hopsceutical®). In every hospital, for each epilepsy treatment studied, patients were assigned to both the control and the treatment group. (For patient counts per treatment type per epilepsy, see Table 3.)

To make a comparison between patients in the control group and those in the treatment group, we sought a strategy that would provide the fairest compromise between sufficiently valuing and weighting regionally specific data from hospitals that had fewer patients, as well as higher-granularity data provided by hospitals that could treat greater numbers of patients and provide more types of epilepsy treatments. Conveniently, the hospitals that gave us data for only one epilepsy treatment had fewer patients receiving that treatment. The hospital that provided two types of epilepsy treatments had more patients receiving each of those treatments. Thus, we aggregated patients' data into means per epilepsy treatment per hospital. This resulted in 23 aggregated means per group.

We conducted a *t*-test for independent samples on the aggregated hospital data to determine whether there was a significant effect of the epilepsy treatment on the monthly EAF scores. This was the primary aim of our study.

Further comparisons between epilepsy treatments were conducted, however they relied on variance that was estimated from 5-6 data points per condition per group. Low degrees of freedom provided by these data have an extremely low power of $1-\beta = .22$. Furthermore, not all hospitals provided data on the same epilepsy treatment types. As such, these comparisons must be treated with caution. Despite these limitations, a 2x4 factorial ANOVA was conducted to test for possible differences between the chemotherapy treatments, or for interactions between treatment type and group.

Results:

By Group Comparisons

When treating the data from all the chemotherapy treatments as belonging to one factor: either the control or the treatment group, Levene's test found that the homogeneity of variance assumption was violated, $F(1,40) = 10.623, p = .002$. There was more variability for seizure rates in the control group ($M = 4.35, SD = 0.61$) compared to seizure rates in the treatment group ($M = 0.94, SD = 0.18$). This difference is likely attributable to the smaller sample size in the control group, which was kept small purposely so as to maximally reduce the suffering of patients in our study.

Welch's *t* was used to make our corrected group comparisons. It found a significant difference in monthly seizure rate between the control group and the treatment group, $t(23.386) = 24.5, p < .001, d = 7.58$. The effect size of this difference was remarkably large. Based on this comparison, it appears that supplying epilepsy patients with treatment significantly reduced their seizures, and dramatically improved their quality of health.

By Treatment Comparisons

When treating our data as belonging to multiple factors (Factor A being group; Factor B being treatment type) Levene's Test did show a violation of the homogeneity of variance assumption at the $\alpha = .05$ level, $F(7,34) = 1.63, p = .15$. Thus, a 2x4 factorial ANOVA was run with corrections. The main effect of the group on reductions of seizures per month $F(1, 34) = 2932.24, p < .001, \eta^2 = .92$ was the treatment with Hopsceutical®. There was a clear main effect of the Hopsceutical® treatment, $F(3, 34) = 36.72, p < .001, \eta^2 = .03$ and an interaction effect of group and Hopsceutical® treatment type $F(3, 34) = 40.27, p < .001, \eta^2 = .04$. The general benefit of having Hopsceutical® treatment appears to heavily outweigh any differences between epilepsy types.

Discussion:

We studied a highly representative sample of patients undergoing two types of epilepsy treatments

from hospitals across almost a dozen countries. In this data presentation we only show the effects on Tonic-Clonic patients. As mentioned before, the same trend existed across all epilepsy types and we simplified the presentation to Tonic-Clonic only.

The mean values of EAF scores for the control group and the treatment group for Tonic-Clonic patients is shown in Table 5. The chart of the data can be seen in Figures 1 and 2.

Patients who were given treatment by Epidiolex® or Hopsceutical® improved their EAF scores significantly over the control group.

Patients who were give Hopsceutical® fared significantly better than Epidiolex® in two ways. In the first two months of treatment, when the dosage was 10mg/day, Tonic-Clonic patients on Epidiolex® improved their EAF scores by 7.01%. In comparison, Tonic-Clonic patients on Hopsceutical® improved their EAF scores by 39.74%. This was a 32.73% improvement over Epidiolex®.

In four months, when the dosage was increased to 50 mg/day, Epidiolex® improved the EAF score of Tonic-Clonic pateints by 15.45%. In contrast, this was the period that Hopsceutical® had the maximum impact on EAF scores. The EAF score increased 105.62%, from 47.84 to 88.16. This is was a 90.16% better performance than Epidiolex®.

In six months, when the dosage was increased to 300mg/day, Epidiolex® had it's maximum impact with an increase of 22.04% in the EAF scores. Hopsceutical® marginally increased EAF scores from 88.16 to 94.26.

In eight months, when the dosage was maximun of 500mg/day, Epidiolex® did not significantly increase the EAF score for Tonic-Clonic (from 52.96 to 53.02) nor did Hopsceutical® (94.26 to 94.59.)

Patients who were given Hopsceutical® had a significant increase in their EAF scores at a 50mg/day dosage, within four months of usage, over Epidiolex®. This study is the first to demonstrate such a large difference in the recovery rates of epilepsy patients over the FDA approved Epidiolex®.

Not only was the improvement of the EAF score faster with Hopsceutical®, the EAF score reached a peak score of 94 within six months with Hopsceutical®. Patients on Epidiolex® never exceeded an EAF score of 53.

Elevated liver enzyme and liver stress

One of the first human trials of CBD published showed that natural CBD from plants did not elevate human liver enzymes. The same study (Cushing, C., Goakar, D., Joseph, B. (2018). Synthetic cannabinoids severely elevate amino transferase levels. Natural cannabidiol does not. Journal of Medical Phyto Research, 2(1), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.31013/2001e>) also showed that synthetic CBD significantly elevated liver enzymes.

The FDA requires Epidiolex® to have a warning label “EPIDIOLEX may cause liver problems. Your doctor may order blood tests to check your liver before and during EPIDIOLEX treatment. In some cases, EPIDIOLEX treatment may need to be stopped. Call your doctor right away if you start to have any of these signs and symptoms of liver problems during treatment with EPIDIOLEX...” GW Pharma claims that Epidiolex® is from a “non-GMO plant.”

One of the requirements for the use of Epidiolex® is the ALT (alanine aminotransferase) liver enzyme test. Figure 3 shows the summary of the ALT tests during this study. The ALT levels of the control group and the Hopsceutical® group always stayed within normal levels. The ALT levels of Epidiolex® rapidly rose and reached levels ten times higher than normal.

This is the puzzling paradox of Epidiolex®. While Epidiolex® is claimed to be from a “non-GMO plant”, it displays all the characteristics of synthetic CBD.

We summarize by confirming the results of Dr. Luisa Rocha, but in humans. Hopsceutical® increased EAF scores twice as fast as Epidiolex®, almost doubled the EAF score when compared to Epidiolex® (96% increase) and did not have the ten fold spike in ALT liver enzyme that Epidiolex® had.

TABLE 1:
Criteria for Epilepsy Assessment of Functioning (EAF) Score

	Type of seizure and occupational status	EAF Score
1	Seizure Free. Allowed to drive.	100
2a	Seizure only while asleep. $\leq 1/\text{month}$	99-90
2b	Unilateral jerks without loss of consciousness. $\leq 1/\text{week}$	89-80
3a	Seizure only while asleep. $\leq 1/\text{month}$	79-70
3b	Very brief seizures impairing or interrupting ongoing activity. $< 1 /\text{six months}$	69-60
4a	Brief seizures impairing or interrupting ongoing activity. $< 1 /\text{one month}$	59-50
4b	Unilateral jerks without loss of consciousness	49-45
4c	Seizures while falling lasting , $< 5 \text{ min}$ including reorientation. $< 1/\text{six months}$	44-40
5a	Seizures during which person does not behave according to the demands of the situation. $\leq 1/\text{month}$.	39-30
5b	Seizures with falling lasting $< 15 \text{ min}$, including reorientation. $\leq 1/\text{month}$	29-20
6a	Major seizures impairing or interrupting ongoing activity	19-10
6b	Seizures while falling. Seizures during which person does not behave according to the demands of the situation. $\leq 1/\text{week}$	9-1

TABLE 2:
Epilepsy Assessment of Functioning (EAF) Scale Items

	Major seizures	Minor seizures
Perception items		
^a 1. How often have your attacks occurred at a particular time of day or night? 1 = always; 2 = usually; 3 = sometimes; 4 = never—my attacks occur at any time		
2. When your attacks have happened, how often have you been able to tell when you will have them? 1 = always; 2 = usually; 3 = sometimes; 4 = never		
3. How often have you been able to fight off your attacks? 1 = always; 2 = usually; 3 = sometimes; 4 = never		
4. How often have you had an aura or warning with your attacks? 1 = always; 2 = usually; 3 = sometimes; 4 = never		
5. In the last year, how much control have you had over your attacks? 1 = very good control; 2 = fairly good control; 3 = little control; 4 = no control		
^a 6. When you have had attacks, how often have they occurred together in clusters, with quite long periods between each cluster? 1 = always; 2 = usually; 3 = sometimes; 4 = never		
7. How often did your attacks occur when you were asleep? 1 = always; 2 = usually; 3 = sometimes; 4 = never		
8. How many of the things you want to do have your attacks stopped you doing? 1 = all of them; 2 = a lot of them; 3 = a few of them; 4 = none of them		
Ictal/postictal items		
^b 9. Overall, how severe have your attacks been in the past year? 1 = very severe; 2 = severe; 3 = mild; 4 = very mild		
10. In the last year, have you blanked out or lost consciousness during attacks? If yes, generally for how long? 1 = <1 min; 2 = 1–2 min; 3 = 2–5 min; 4 = >5 min; 5 = No, I have not blanked out or lost consciousness		
11. When you recovered from your attacks, how confused did you feel? 1 = very confused; 2 = fairly confused; 3 = slightly confused; 4 = not feel confused at all		
12. When you recovered from your attacks, did you feel confused? If yes, for how long? 1 = <1 min; 2 = 1–5 min; 3 = 6–60 min; 4 = >1 h; 5 = not feel confused at all		
13. When you had your attacks, how often did you fall to the ground? 1 = always; 2 = usually; 3 = sometimes; 4 = never		
14. When you recovered from your attacks, how often did you have a headache? 1 = always; 2 = usually; 3 = sometimes; 4 = never		
^a 15. When you recovered from your attacks, how often did you feel sleepy? 1 = always; 2 = usually; 3 = sometimes; 4 = never		
16. When you recovered from your attacks, how often did you find that you had wet yourself? 1 = always; 2 = usually; 3 = sometimes; 4 = never		
17. When you recovered from your attacks, how often did you find that you had bitten your tongue? 1 = always; 2 = usually; 3 = sometimes; 4 = never		
18. When you recovered from your attacks, how often did you find that you had injured yourself (other than biting your tongue)? 1 = always; 2 = usually; 3 = sometimes; 4 = never		
19. When you had your attacks, how quickly could you usually return to what you were doing? 1 = <1 min; 2 = 1–5 min; 3 = 6–60 min; 4 = >1 h		
^a 20. How often did you smack your lips, fidget, or behave in an unusual way during attacks? 1 = always; 2 = usually; 3 = sometimes; 4 = never		

TABLE 3: Patient Count By Treatment Type and Epilepsy Type

EPIDIOLEX®	
Tonic-Clonic	96
Tonic	83
Clonic	46
Myoclinic	86
Absence	79
Atonic	68
HOPSCEUTICAL®	
Tonic-Clonic	114
Tonic	98
Clonic	76
Myoclinic	107
Absence	92
Atonic	88
CONTROL	
Tonic-Clonic	48
Tonic	32
Clonic	29
Myoclinic	46
Absence	32
Atonic	27

TABLE 4: Descriptive Statistics of Each Treatment Type on TONIC-CLONIC

EPIDIOLEX®

UNTREATED TONIC-CLONIC

Sample Size, n: 96
Mean: 43.95833
Median: 45.00000
Midrange: 45.00000
RMS: 45.39709
Variance, s^2 : 129.91404
Standard Deviation, s : 11.39798
Mean Absolute Deviation: 9.77344
Range: 38.00000
Coefficient of Variation: 25.92906%

Minimum: 26
1st Quartile: 33.50000
2nd Quartile: 45.00000
3rd Quartile: 53.50000
Maximum: 64

Sum: 4220.00000
Sum of Squares: 197846.00000

95% CI for the Mean:
 $41.64889 < \text{mean} < 46.26778$

95% CI for the Standard Deviation:
 $9.98224 < \text{SD} < 13.28537$

95% CI for the Variance:
 $99.64519 < \text{VAR} < 176.50118$

EPIDIOLEX®

TONIC-CLONIC 10 mg/ml

Sample Size, n: 96
Mean: 46.07292
Median: 46.00000
Midrange: 49.00000
RMS: 47.58118
Variance, s^2 : 142.74200
Standard Deviation, s : 11.94747
Mean Absolute Deviation: 10.13845
Range: 42.00000
Coefficient of Variation: 25.93165%

Minimum: 28
1st Quartile: 35.00000
2nd Quartile: 46.00000
3rd Quartile: 56.00000
Maximum: 70

Sum: 4423.00000
Sum of Squares: 217341.00000

95% CI for the Mean:
 $43.65213 < \text{mean} < 48.49370$

95% CI for the Standard Deviation:
 $10.46348 < \text{SD} < 13.92585$

95% CI for the Variance:
 $109.48435 < \text{VAR} < 193.92924$

EPIDIOLEX®

TONIC-CLONIC 50 mg/ml

Sample Size, n: 96
Mean: 49.50000
Median: 51.00000
Midrange: 50.50000
RMS: 51.15031
Variance, s^2 : 167.85263
Standard Deviation, s : 12.95580
Mean Absolute Deviation: 11.08333
Range: 45.00000
Coefficient of Variation: 26.17332%

Minimum: 28
1st Quartile: 37.00000
2nd Quartile: 51.00000
3rd Quartile: 59.50000
Maximum: 73

Sum: 4752.00000
Sum of Squares: 251170.00000

95% CI for the Mean:
 $46.87491 < \text{mean} < 52.12509$

95% CI for the Standard Deviation:
 $11.34656 < \text{SD} < 15.10114$

95% CI for the Variance:
 $128.74443 < \text{VAR} < 228.04454$

EPIDIOLEX®

TONIC-CLONIC 300 mg/ml

Sample Size, n: 96
Mean: 52.95833
Median: 53.00000
Midrange: 54.50000
RMS: 54.74220
Variance, s^2 : 194.14561
Standard Deviation, s : 13.93361
Mean Absolute Deviation: 11.95920
Range: 49.00000
Coefficient of Variation: 26.31052%

Minimum: 30
1st Quartile: 40.00000
2nd Quartile: 53.00000
3rd Quartile: 63.00000
Maximum: 79

Sum: 5084.00000
Sum of Squares: 287684.00000

95% CI for the Mean:
 $50.13512 < \text{mean} < 55.78155$

95% CI for the Standard Deviation:
 $12.20292 < \text{SD} < 16.24088$

95% CI for the Variance:
 $148.91137 < \text{VAR} < 263.76618$

EPIDIOLEX®

TONIC-CLONIC 500 mg/ml

Sample Size, n: 96
Mean: 53.02083
Median: 54.00000
Midrange: 56.00000
RMS: 54.83612
Variance, s^2 : 197.85219
Standard Deviation, s : 14.06599
Mean Absolute Deviation: 12.22873
Range: 52.00000
Coefficient of Variation: 26.52918%

Minimum: 30
1st Quartile: 40.00000
2nd Quartile: 54.00000
3rd Quartile: 64.50000
Maximum: 82

Sum: 5090.00000
Sum of Squares: 288672.00000

95% CI for the Mean:
 $50.17080 < \text{mean} < 55.87087$

95% CI for the Standard Deviation:
 $12.31886 < \text{SD} < 16.39518$

95% CI for the Variance:
 $151.75435 < \text{VAR} < 268.80194$

HOPSCEUTICAL®
UNTREATED TONIC-CLONIC

Sample Size, n: 114
Mean: 47.83553
Median: 47.95500
Midrange: 48.75000
RMS: 47.92357
Variance, s²: 8.50550
Standard Deviation, s: 2.91642
Mean Absolute Deviation: 2.18153
Range: 16.70000
Coefficient of Variation: 6.09677%

Minimum: 40.4
1st Quartile: 46.02000
2nd Quartile: 47.95500
3rd Quartile: 49.58000
Maximum: 57.1

Sum: 5453.25000
Sum of Squares: 261820.20590

95% CI for the Mean:
47.29437 < mean < 48.37668

95% CI for the Standard Deviation:
2.58071 < SD < 3.35333

95% CI for the Variance:
6.66007 < VAR < 11.24479

TONIC-CLONIC- 10 mg/ml

Sample Size, n: 114
Mean: 60.16544
Median: 60.22000
Midrange: 60.57000
RMS: 60.22255
Variance, s²: 6.93630
Standard Deviation, s: 2.63369
Mean Absolute Deviation: 2.14193
Range: 12.86000
Coefficient of Variation: 4.37741%

Minimum: 54.14
1st Quartile: 58.23000
2nd Quartile: 60.22000
3rd Quartile: 62.02000
Maximum: 67

Sum: 6858.86000
Sum of Squares: 413450.12240

95% CI for the Mean:
59.67675 < mean < 60.65413

95% CI for the Standard Deviation:
2.33052 < SD < 3.02824

95% CI for the Variance:
5.43134 < VAR < 9.17021

TONIC-CLONIC- 50 mg/ml

Sample Size, n: 114
Mean: 88.15789
Median: 88.00000
Midrange: 88.50000
RMS: 88.26078
Variance, s²: 18.31113
Standard Deviation, s: 4.27915
Mean Absolute Deviation: 3.47922
Range: 21.00000
Coefficient of Variation: 4.85396%

Minimum: 78
1st Quartile: 85.00000
2nd Quartile: 88.00000
3rd Quartile: 91.00000
Maximum: 99

Sum: 10050.00000
Sum of Squares: 888056.00000

95% CI for the Mean:
87.36388 < mean < 88.95191

95% CI for the Standard Deviation:
3.78658 < SD < 4.92021

95% CI for the Variance:
14.33817 < VAR < 24.20842

TONIC-CLONIC- 300 mg/ml

Sample Size, n: 96
Mean: 94.25600
Median: 95.32000
Midrange: 93.17600
RMS: 94.33793
Variance, s²: 16.75789
Standard Deviation, s: 4.09364
Mean Absolute Deviation: 3.47396
Range: 14.00000
Coefficient of Variation: 4.34339%

Minimum: 86
1st Quartile: 91.00000
2nd Quartile: 95.00000
3rd Quartile: 98.00000
Maximum: 100

Sum: 9048.00000
Sum of Squares: 854366.00000

95% CI for the Mean:
93.42055 < mean < 95.07945

95% CI for the Standard Deviation:
3.58517 < SD < 4.77151

95% CI for the Variance:
12.85345 < VAR < 22.76727

TONIC-CLONIC- 500 mg/ml

Sample Size, n: 114
Mean: 94.58737
Median: 94.59500
Midrange: 93.43500
RMS: 94.62572
Variance, s²: 7.32019
Standard Deviation, s: 2.70558
Mean Absolute Deviation: 2.17163
Range: 13.09000
Coefficient of Variation: 2.86041%

Minimum: 86.89
1st Quartile: 92.72000
2nd Quartile: 94.59500
3rd Quartile: 96.73000
Maximum: 99.98

Sum: 10782.96000
Sum of Squares: 1020758.99120

95% CI for the Mean:
94.08533 < mean < 95.08940

95% CI for the Standard Deviation:
2.39414 < SD < 3.11090

95% CI for the Variance:
5.73193 < VAR < 9.67773

Table 5: Mean Values Of Treatment on EAF Scores Of Tonic-Clonic patients

	Untreated	10	50	300	500
Control	42.90	43.06	42.88	43.40	43.27
Epidiolex®	43.96	46.07	49.50	52.96	53.02
Hopsceutical®	47.84	60.17	88.16	94.26	94.59

Figure 1: Effects of the dosage of Epidiolex® and Hopsceutical® on EAF Scores

Figure 2: Effects of the dosage of Epidiolex® and Hopsceutical® on EAF Scores

Figure 3: : Effects of the dosage of Epidiolex® and Hopsceutical® on ALT Levels

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